

Green Synthesis of Calcium Oxide Nanoparticles using *Murraya Koenigii* Leaf (Curry Leaves) Extract for Photo-Degradation of Methyl Red and Methyl Blue

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Abstract:- Dyes are the main input as a coloring agent for textile and some other industries. When these wastewaters enter into nearby marine environment, it can harm marine species and pollute the whole freshwater ecosystem. So, treatment of these industrial effluents is necessary before discharging it to the environment. Currently, we have synthesis a non-toxic and biogenic CaO nanoparticle from the leaves of *Murraya koenigii* leaves. Then the nanoparticles were characterized using UV, FTIR, XRD, SEM and TEM. The UV data shows absorbance at 345 nm. While the obtained band gap was about 2.5 eV. Further, characterization tests confirmed the formation of CaO nanoparticles. CaO nanoparticles was applied for treatment of methyl red and methyl blue dyes solutions under UV light and without UV light in order to check its degradation capability. Methyl red degradation was slow as compared to methyl blue. The results obtained shows that, under UV light the synthesized nanoparticles fully degrade methyl blue in 20 minutes. Whereas, 70% methyl red was degraded in 60 minutes under UV light. While, without UV light the degradation was about 10% for methyl blue and 5% for methyl red respectively.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since 1856, after the discovery of first synthetic dye, about 10000 new dyes has been produced until now. While, approximately 70%-75% of these dyes are azo dye. Which are considered very hazardous for human health. Methyl red and methyl blue is also an azo dye and contain aromatic and $-N = N-$ groups in their molecules. It is very toxic for humans, plants and animals. It can cause a series of human health problems including cancer, birth defects, allergies and endocrine disruption (Zhou et al., 2021a).

These dyes are mainly used by textile industries as a coloring agent. Every year more than 800000 tons of dyes are produced and utilized for coloring purposes. However, during dye-processing major portion of dyes are lost in the form of wastewater. These dyes-containing wastewater are released to fresh water bodies. Where these wastewaters mix-up with clean water and contaminate the little available fresh water and put hazardous effects on humans, flora and fauna of the

earth. Therefore, its proper treatment is necessary before discharging it to environment (Zhou et al., 2021b).

Nanotechnology is a new, advanced and promising for treatment of pollutions. Nanoscience is today on the path of generating new, advanced and sustainable materials. Traditionally, Nanoparticles and nanomaterials have been made using chemical and physical process. However, these nanoparticles were toxic, expensive and unsustainable for application in the field of Environment and several others. Currently, scientists are exploring biological approach for synthesis of nanoparticles. (Jyoti and Singh, 2016)

Bio-nanoparticles are those nanoparticles composed from biological sources such as plants, bacteria, Fungai and yeast. An extensive work has been done on synthesis of green nanoparticles from various biological sources (Jyoti and Singh, 2016) (Saravanan et al., 2017) (Sriramulu and Sumathi, 2018) (Nadaf and Kanase, 2019). While its treatments capabilities of dyes in aqueous media was also studied. Most commonly, metals oxides and plants extracts are mixed with each other as a precursor and reducing agent for synthesise of various metals-based nanoparticles. However, some researches show that, these metals-based nanoparticles can put adverse effects on living cell and can damage DNA, cell membrane and electron transport chain (Griffitt et al., 2008) (Rana et al., 2020).

Green Calcium oxide is considered as non-toxic, cheap, efficient, sustainable and suitable for application in the treatment of wastewater. (Jaiswal et al., 2021) synthesized CaO nanoparticles from eggs shell and applied it for photocatalysis of methyl blue. The results indicated that 98% of methyl blue was degraded in 180 minutes. However, plant extract based CaO nanoparticle is not fully explored for degradation of methyl red.

In this research, we have synthesized a green calcium nanoparticle from the leaves extract of *Murraya Koenigii* (curry) plant and evaluate its photodegradation capabilities of Methyl red and methyl blue dye.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Synthesis of CaO nanoparticle

Firstly, for preparation of leaves extract, we take 50 grams of dried *Murraya Koenigii* plant leaves, wash it with distilled water and cut it into more small pieces. While boiled it in 100 ml distilled water for about 1 hour. After boiling, the solution was filtered using filter paper and get the extract of *Murraya Koenigii* plant leaves.

Secondly, 2 grams of Calcium Chloride was dissolved in 20 ml distilled water. The solution of calcium chloride was added to 30ml plant extract and was stirred using a magnetic stirrer for one hour. While 4 grams NaOH was dissolved in 40 ml distilled water and was added drop wise to the solution during stirring.

Finally, the stirred solution was filtered using filter paper and the obtained precipitate was dried in an oven for 3 hours at 100 C°. Then the dried precipitate was calcinated for 3 hours at 400 C° (Bano and Pillai, 2020).

B. Characterization

Characterization was done using various instruments and characterization technique to examine the physiochemical properties of the prepared CaO nanoparticle. These techniques include UV-Visible spectroscopy, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM).

C. Photocatalytic degradation setup

An experiment on the photocatalytic degradation of methyl blue and methyl red was carried out in order to know

the degradation ability of green CaO nanoparticle. 50mg dye was dissolving into 100 ml distilled water. While 10mg CaO nanoparticles was added to the dye solution along with 5ml of 0.05 mole NaBH₄. The solution was stirred using magnetic stirrer under 100-watt bulb and samples were taken after every 5 minutes. Finally, all samples were tested.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Characterization of nanoparticles

The synthesized nanoparticles were characterized in order to know the physical and chemical characteristics of the prepared nanoparticles.

➤ UV-visible absorption

During reaction, when we added reducing agent the color of the reaction was changed from green to yellow and after calcination the color of the particles changed from yellow to gray clearly indicating that reducing agent was involved in reaction and particles were properly calcinated. Further analysis was done using UV-visible absorption spectrometer in order to confirm the formation of CaO nanoparticle. A small amount of CaO nanoparticles was dissolved in distilled water and the sample was sonicated for 2 minutes and then UV was performed. The UV spectra absorbance was peaked at 345 nm. The sharp peak visibly representing the characteristic of a nanoparticle. The band gap of the synthesized nanoparticle was also calculated using Tauc plot method. The obtained band gap was about 2.5 eV. The smaller band gap material performs better in a photocatalytic activity. Because, the excitation of electron depends upon the band gap. The smaller the band gap, the easily will be the excitation of electron from valence band to the conduction band.

Fig 1 : UV-VIS graph and Band gap

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy of CaO nanoparticle was performed in the range of 4000 cm⁻¹ to 600 cm⁻¹ in order to know about different functional groups present on the surface of the nanoparticles. The FTIR spectra Shows that the sharp peaks were found at 1394.54 cm⁻¹, 871.82 cm⁻¹ and 711.73 cm⁻¹ respectively. These peaks indicate the presence of C–O, C–C, Ca–O linkage etc in the nanoparticle. The Sharp peak at 1394.54 cm⁻¹ and at 871.82 cm⁻¹ suggests the presence of C-O and C-C bond

which can be appointed to the carbonation of CaO nanoparticles. While a sharp peak at 711.73 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of Ca–O bonding which can be attributed to the presence of calcium oxide.

Fig 2: Fourier Transform infrared spectroscopy graph.

➤ X-ray Diffraction (XRD)

X-ray Diffraction (XRD) Analysis were performed to identify the crystallinity and nanosize of the prepared CaO nanoparticle in the spectrum range of 10° to 60° . The X-ray diffraction patterns shows sharps and definite X-ray diffraction peaks. Which clarify that particles size of the prepared CaO nanoparticles were in the nanoscale range. The observed diffraction peaks located at 23.0° , 29.4° , 31.4° , 35.9° , 39.4° , 43.1° , 45.5° , 47.5° , 48.5° , 56.3° , and 57.4° are found in good agreement with standard JCPDS data NO.77-2,376. The Crystallinity of the prepared nanoparticles were calculated using the Debye-Scherrer formula ($D = K\lambda/\beta \cos \theta$), where D is the average particle size, k is the Scherrer constant (0.94 for spherical particles), λ is the wavelength (1.54Å), and β is the FWHM (full width at half-maximum). The crystallite size of the most intense peak located at 29.3° is about 31.65 nm and the crystallite size of the lowest peak located at 56.3° is about 0.34 nm. While the average crystallite size is 3.89 nm.

Fig 3: XRD graph

➤ Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was performed to assess the morphology and particle size of the CaO nanoparticle. The SEM micrographs indicates that the particles are in irregular shape. Additionally, its distributions are nonuniform and looks like a cluster because of agglomerations of particles. While the size of the particles is ranging from 6.3 nm to 18.3 nm and the average particle size is about 9.9 nm.

Fig 4: Scanning Electron Microscopy

➤ *Energy-Dispersive X-ray (EDX)*

Energy-Dispersive X-ray Analysis (EDX) was performed in order to identify the elemental composition of CaO. The EDX clearly reveal the formation of CaO nanoparticles. The total Percentage of Ca was about 24.54% while the percentage of oxygen was 50.14 %. While the presence of C was due to plant extract and Na and Cl due to the chemicals used in the reaction.

Fig 5: Energy-Dispersive X-ray

B. Analysis of Photodegradation Properties of Nanoparticles

The CaO nanoparticles were applied for degradation of azo dyes under UV light source and without UV light source to assess the photodegradation property of nanoparticles.

➤ *Degradation of dyes with UV light*

In order to test the dyes degradation capability of calcium oxide nanoparticles, the photocatalytic activity was carried out on methyl blue and methyl red. Methyl blue and methyl red solution was prepared by dissolving 50 mg dye in 100 ml distilled water and the initial absorption peak was recorded for both dyes using UV- Visible spectrometer. While only 10mg CaO nanoparticle was added along with 5ml of 0.05 mole NaBH₄. Both solutions were stirred under 100-watt bulb and samples were taken after every 5 minutes and investigated using UV- Visible spectrometer. Methyl blue was fully degraded in 20 minutes. The degradation percentage of methyl blue was the same in every sample. Methyl red was initially degraded very fast and slowed down with time. While after 60 minutes further degradation was almost constant.

Fig 6: Methyl blue photodegradation and effects of time

Fig 7: Methyl red photodegradation and effects of time

➤ Degradation of dyes without UV light

An experiment on the degradation of dyes without UV light was carried in order to know about the absorption capacity of the synthesized nanoparticles. Dyes solutions of Methyl red and methyl blue were prepared by dissolving 50 mg dye in 100 ml distilled water and the initial absorption peak was recorded for both dyes using UV- Visible spectrometer. While only 10mg CaO nanoparticle was added along with 5ml of 0.05 mole NaBH₄. Both solutions were kept in dark for about 2 hours and samples were taken from both solution after every 30 minutes. The results show that, the absorption capacity of CaO with UV is very low. Methyl red was degraded up to 5% in 120 minutes and after 120 minutes the same peak was observed showing no more degradation. Similarly, about 10% methyl blue was degraded in 180 minutes. While after 180 minutes the degradation was stopped as shown in the following figures.

Fig 8: Methyl blue and methyl red degradation in dark

IV. CONCLUSION

Nanoparticles and nanomaterials have very great potential. Biobased Calcium oxide nanoparticle are cheap and non-toxic to humans and all other species.

- (1) We synthesized a biobased CaO nanoparticle in this study. The prepared nanoparticles were characterized for physicals and chemicals characteristics. The UV-VIS spectroscopy data reveals the formation of good and stable nanoparticles. The FTIR and TEM data further clarify the presence of calcium and oxygen bond and calcium oxygen contents respectively. While, XRD and SEM shows that the synthesized nanoparticles are in nano size.
- (2) It has the potential to degrade dyes and majority of other pollutants. The synthesized CaO nanoparticles fully degrade methyl blue in 20 minutes under UV light. While, only 70% methyl red was degraded in 60 minutes under UV light. Whereas, without UV light the degradation was about 10% for methyl blue and 5% for methyl red respectively.

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